

A Framework for Implementing Role-based Access Control Using CORBA Security Service*

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Abstract

The paper shows how role-based access control (RBAC) models could be implemented using CORBA Security service. A configuration of CORBA protection system is defined. We provide definitions of $RBAC_0$ and $RBAC_1$ implementations in the framework of CORBA Security and describe what is required from an implementation of CORBA Security service in order to support $RBAC_0$ - $RBAC_3$ models.

1 Introduction

Role-based access control (RBAC) [SCFY96] is a family of reference models in which permissions are associated with roles and users are assigned to appropriate roles. A role can represent competency, authority, responsibility or specific duty assignments. Some variations of RBAC include the capability to establish relations between roles, between permissions and roles, and between users and roles. There are four established RBAC reference models: unrelated roles ($RBAC_0$), role-hierarchies ($RBAC_1$), user and role assignment constraints ($RBAC_2$), and both

hierarchies and constraints ($RBAC_3$). RBAC supports three security principals: least privilege, separation of duties and data abstraction.

A major purpose of RBAC is to facilitate access control administration and review. RBAC is a promising approach to address the needs of the commercial enterprises better than lattice-based MAC [BL75] and owner-based DAC [Lam71]. Recent series of papers describe ways to model or implement RBAC using the technologies employed by the commercial users: Oracle [Not95], NetWare [ES95], Java [Giu98], DG/UX [Mey97], object-oriented systems [Bar95], object-oriented databases [Won97], M-S Windows NT [BC98], enterprise security management systems [Awi97]. Evidence of RBAC recognition in the US government is the fact that the proposed rules on security from the Department of Health and Human Services [Dep98] include RBAC as one of the required alternatives for access control.

At the same time, the commercial market is experiencing the spread of systems based on Common Object Request Broker Architecture (CORBA) technology. CORBA is a versatile object-based distributed computing technology, which is becoming a worldwide industry standard for constructing distributed software systems. CORBA standardization process is based on the consensus of over 800 software companies. The computing model that CORBA adheres to is outlined in Object Management Architecture (OMA) [SS95]. The CORBA environment, including CORBA Security Service, provides a general-purpose infrastructure for developing and deploying distributed object systems in a broad range of specialized vertical domains. CORBA Security service (CS) defines the interfaces to a collection of objects for enforcing a range of security policies using diverse security mechanisms. It provides abstraction from an underlying

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security technology so that CORBA-based applications could be independent from the particular security infrastructure provided by a user enterprise computing environment. Due to its general nature, CS is not tailored to any particular access control model. Instead, it defines a general mechanism which is supposed to be adequate for the majority of cases and could be configured to support various access control models. For example, it is shown in [Kar96] how to implement lattice-based MAC using the CORBA authorization model. In the next few years we expect to witness significant financial investments in the enterprise-wide deployment of CS in commercial and government organizations, including those who will construct their security policies utilizing RBAC concepts. It is important to foresee if CS will fully support RBAC models. However, we are not aware of any work in the research community that has explored the potential of CS for support of RBAC reference models.

In this paper we present an approach for implementing RBAC models using the access control mechanism provided by CS. We define a configuration of CS protection system. Then we define RBAC₀ and RBAC₁ implementations in terms of CS framework and describe how RBAC₀-RBAC₃ could be implemented in CS. We illustrate the discussion with several examples. Our approach allows an implementation compliant with CS specification to support RBAC₀. Additional functionality, which is beyond CS specification scope, should be implemented in order to support RBAC₁ and/or RBAC₂.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the access control model of CS and defines a configuration of the CORBA protection system; Section 3 defines RBAC models using CS concepts and shows a possible implementation of RBAC₀-RBAC₃ using CS with illustration on an example role hierarchy; Section 4 concludes the paper.

2 CORBA Access Control Model

In this section, we first informally describe the CORBA Access Control model. Then, we formally define a configuration of the CORBA Protection System state.

2.1 Informal Description

The CORBA environment, including CORBA Security Service, provides a general-purpose infrastructure for developing and deploying distributed object-based systems in a broad range of specialized vertical domains. All enti-

ties in the CORBA computing model are identified with interfaces defined in the OMG Interface Definition Language (IDL). A CORBA interface is a collection of three things: operations, attributes, and exceptions. An implementation of a CORBA interface is called a CORBA object. Hence, we use “CORBA object” or just “object” to mean “implementation of a CORBA interface”, where it does not cause confusion. Object functionality is exposed to other CORBA-based applications only through the corresponding interfaces. Objects have object references by which they can be referenced. An object reference is a handle through which one requests operations on the object.

The CS model comprises the following functionalities visible to application developers and security administrators: identification and authentication, authorization and access control, auditing, integrity and confidentiality protection, authentication of clients and target objects, optional non-repudiation, administration of security policies and related information.

One of the objectives of CS is to be totally unobtrusive to application developers. Security-unaware objects should be able to run securely on a secure ORB without any active involvement on the site of application objects. In the meantime, it must be possible for security-aware objects to exercise stricter security policies than the ones enforced by CS. In the CS model, all object invocations are mediated by the appropriate security functions in order to enforce various security policies such as access control. A simplified schema of control points in CS model is represented in Figure 1. Those functions are part of CS and are tightly integrated with the ORB because all messages between CORBA objects and clients are passed through the ORB.

CS uses the notion of principal. “A *principal* is a human user or system entity that is registered in and authentic to the system” [Obj98]. In translation to the traditional security terminology, a principal is a subject. CS manages access control policies based on the security attributes of principals and attributes of objects as well as operations implemented by those objects. Objects that have common security requirements are grouped in security policy domains. Access control policies control what principals can invoke what operations on what objects in the domain the policies are defined on. Policies can be enforced either by the ORB or by the application. In the latter case, such an application is called a *security-aware application*. Domains allow application of access control policies to security-unaware objects without requiring changes to their implementations or interfaces.

Figure 1: Access Control Points in CORBA Security Service (from [Obj98])

As it can be seen in Figure 1, the client-side and target-side invocation access policy governs whether the client can invoke the requested operation on the target object on behalf of the current principal. This policy is enforced by the ORB in cooperation with the security service it uses for all (security-aware and unaware) applications. A client may invoke an operation on the target object as specified in the request only if this is allowed by the object invocation access policy.

A user uses a *UserSponsor*¹ to authenticate to the CS environment (Figure 2). A *UserSponsor* authenticates on

Figure 2: User Authentication

behalf of a user with and obtains authenticated credentials from a *PrincipalAuthenticator*. Instances of *UserSponsor* implement user interface specific to the authentication method supported by the concrete implementation of CS. For example, for password-based authentication,

¹A *UserSponsor* is an implementation artifact which handles the user authentication process.

it prompts the user for user name and password. For authentication based on smart-cards, it interacts with a smart-card reader and (probably) prompts the user to insert the card in the reader. CS standard does not mandate any particular authentication method. What it does specify is the interface of a *PrincipalAuthenticator*. A *PrincipalAuthenticator* conducts the actual authentication and creates *Credentials* object for a new principal. Based on the authentication data it received from a *UserSponsor* and on the underlying security technology (Kerberos, SESAME, or any other capable technology) as well as on any rules it adheres to, *PrincipalAuthenticator* instantiates *Credentials* with various information. The information in *Credentials* constitute the identity of the new principal which initiates requests on CORBA objects on behalf of the user. Principal authenticated security attributes are part of the information stored in the *Credentials* object.

The concept of a user is absent from CS AC model. Instead a principal represents the user completely. The notion of a session is indistinguishable from the notion of a principal. Thus multiple principals can act on behalf of a single user. They all potentially have different sets of credentials and therefore exist in CS as completely independent entities. Among other data, principal credentials contain security attributes. Hereafter, we understand attribute to mean security attribute. From the CS AC model point of view, a principal is nothing but an unordered collection of authenticated attributes. All attributes are typed. Attribute types are partitioned into two families: privilege attributes and identity attributes. The family of privilege attributes enumerates attribute

types that identify principal privileges: access identifier, primary and secondary groups the principal is a member of, clearance, capabilities, etc. Identity attributes, if present, provide additional information about the principal: audit id, accounting id, and non-repudiation id, reflecting the fact that a principal might have various identities used for different purposes. Principal credentials may contain zero or more attributes of the same family or type.² An example of security attributes assigned to authenticated principals is provided in Table 1. One of the standard CORBA attribute types is the *role* attribute. Due to the extensibility of the schema for defining security attributes, an implementation of CS can support attribute types that are not defined by the CORBA Security standard. Although the normative part of CS does not mandate the way attributes are managed, assignment of such attributes to users is meant to be performed by user administrators.

Principal	Attributes
p_1	a_1
p_2	a_2, a_6
p_3	a_2, a_3
p_4	a_4, a_5

Table 1: Security Attributes Possessed by Authenticated Principals

All a principal does in the CORBA computational model is invoke operations on corresponding objects. In order to make a request one needs to know two things: object reference, which uniquely identifies an object, and operation name. CORBA interfaces can inherit from other CORBA interfaces via interface inheritance. An operation name is unique for an interface.³ Thus, any operation is uniquely identified by its name and by the name of the interface it is defined in.

In this paper, we use notation $i_k m_n$, to refer to n -th operation on k -th interface.

There is a global⁴ set of *required rights* for each operation defined by its interface’s required rights mapping. This set, together with a combinator (all or any rights), defines what rights a principal has to have in order

²This rule applies to all attribute types including access id, although it is hard to foresee a useful implementation of CS where a principal would have multiple or no access identities.

³Interface inheritance in CORBA does not allow to inherit from interfaces with operations of the same type. This rule resolves the problem of operation name overloading.

⁴I.e. not dependent on a policy domain in which the object is located.

to invoke the operation. Table 2 provides an example of required rights for operations on three interfaces i_1 , i_2 , and i_3 . It is assumed that required rights are defined and their semantics are precisely documented by application developers who know the best what each operation does. Depending on the access policy (*DomainAccessPolicy*) enforced in a particular AC policy domain,⁵ a principal is granted different rights (*GrantedRights*) according to what *SecurityAttributes* it has.⁶ Each *DomainAccessPolicy* defines what rights are granted for each security attribute. An example of a mapping between principal privilege attributes and granted rights is provided in Table 3. Security administrators are responsible

Attributes	Granted Rights	
	Domain	
	d_1	d_2
a_1	r_1	r_2
a_2	-	r_1
a_3	r_2, r_3	-
a_4	r_3	r_1, r_4
a_5	r_1, r_2, r_3	r_2, r_3, r_4
a_6	r_6	r_1

Table 3: Granted Rights per Attribute

for defining what rights are granted to what security attributes in what delegation state on domain per domain basis. Whenever a principal attempts an operation invocation, principal’s effective rights are computed via operation *AccessPolicy::get_effective_rights*.⁷ CS specification purposefully does not define how the operation combines rights granted through different privilege attribute entries in Table 3. The specifiers let CS implementors define the operation’s internal behavior ([Obj98, p. 122]). A simplest implementation of *get_effective_rights* could be when the set of rights granted to a principal is a union of rights granted to every security attribute the principal has. For our examples, we will assume exactly this implementation of the operation. If we use our example of security attributes assigned to principals p_1 , p_2 , p_3 , and p_4 (Table 1), and the examples of required (Table 2) and granted (Table 3) rights, then Table 4 shows what rights the principals are granted in each domain.

⁵In the CORBA security model, a security policy domain is just a collection of objects.

⁶For the sake of brevity, we omit delegation state qualifier for granted rights. This does not change the correctness of the discussion, as we show below.

⁷Regular caching techniques can be used by an implementation to avoid repetitive computations.

Operations	Required Rights	Combinator	Meaning
i_1m_1	r_1	all	Only a principal who is granted right r_1 can invoke the operation.
i_1m_2	r_1, r_2	any	Any principal who is granted either r_1 or r_2 right can invoke the operation.
i_2m_1	r_2, r_3	all	Only a principal who is granted both r_2 and r_3 rights can invoke the operation.
i_2m_2	r_2, r_3, r_4	all	Only a principal who is granted all r_2, r_3, r_4 rights can invoke the operation.
i_3m_1	r_1, r_2, r_3, r_4	any	Any principal who is granted either of r_1, r_2, r_3, r_4 rights can invoke the operation.

Table 2: Required Rights Matrix

Principal	Granted Rights	
	Domains	
	d_1	d_2
p_1	r_1	r_2
p_2	r_6	r_1
p_3	r_2, r_3	r_1
p_4	r_1, r_2, r_3	r_1, r_2, r_3, r_4

Table 4: Granted Rights Per Principal

2.2 CORBA Protection State Configuration

We summarize the above description of the CS AC model by defining the protection state configuration of a CORBA system:

Definition 2.1 A configuration of a CORBA system protection state is the thirteen-tuple $(A, IM, O, R, D, C, RRM, DS, IDM, GRM, effective_rights, combine, interface_operation)$ interpreted as follows:

- A is the set of privilege attributes.
- IM is the set of operations uniquely identified by interfaces that they are defined on.
- O is a set of distinguishable interface instances.
- R is the set of rights.
- D is the set of access policy domains.
- $C = \{all, any\}$ is a set of rights combinators.
- RRM is the required rights matrix, with a row for every interface operation from IM and two columns. For the first column (Required Rights), we have $[IM, Rights] \subseteq R$. For the second column (Combinator), we have $[IM, Combinator] \in C$.
- $DS = \{i, d\}$ is a set of delegation states.
- IDM is the matrix of domain membership for interface instances with a row for every domain from D and a column for every interface instance from O . We denote the contents of the (D, O) cell of IDM by $[D, O]$. We have $[D, O] \subseteq \{T, F\}$ ⁸, $[d, o] == T \implies o \in d$.
- GRM is the granted rights matrix, with a row for every attribute from A and a column for every access policy domain from D . We denote the contents of the (A, D) cell of GRM by $[A, D]$. We have $[A, D] \subseteq R$.
- $effective_rights$: $D \times 2^A \longrightarrow 2^R$, a function mapping a set a_1, a_2, \dots, a_l of privilege attributes (where $\forall 1 < i < l : a_i \in A$) in a domain $d_j \in D$ to a set of rights r_1, r_2, \dots, r_p (where $\forall i, 1 < i < p : r_i \in R$) that are in effect for the given set of attributes.
- $combine$: $2^D \times 2^R \longrightarrow 2^R$, a function mapping sets of rights returned from $effective_rights$ for every domain in D the interface instance is a member of, to a set of effective rights.
- $interface_operation$: $M \times O \longrightarrow IM$, a function mapping an operation name m and an interface instance $o \in O$ into an interface operation uniquely identified on the interface, which o implements.

□

⁸ T stands for true and F stands for false.

Function *effective_rights* looks up *GRM* to obtain granted rights for each attribute in all domains to which *o* belongs. It combines those rights according to its implementation and returns effective rights for each domain. Results returned from *effective_rights* serve as input parameters for the function *combine*. The latter combines them according to its implementation. Rights returned by *combine* are checked against *RRM*. If the match succeeds, then access is granted. Otherwise, access is denied.

Table 5 shows what operations can be invoked by the principals from our example. For each domain, an ac-

Principals	Operations	
	Domains	
	d_1	d_2
p_1	i_1m_1, i_1m_2	i_1m_2
p_2	-	i_1m_1, i_1m_2
p_3	i_1m_2, i_2m_1	i_1m_1, i_1m_2
p_4	i_1m_1, i_1m_2, i_2m_1	$i_1m_1, i_1m_2, i_2m_1, i_2m_2, i_3m_1$

Table 5: Operations that a Principal Can Invoke

cess matrix from [Lam71], such as in Table 6, could be constructed.

Subjects	Objects		
	i_1	i_2	i_3
p_1	i_1m_2		
p_2	i_1m_1, i_1m_2		
p_3	i_1m_1, i_1m_2		
p_4	i_1m_1, i_1m_2	i_2m_1, i_2m_2	i_3m_1

Table 6: Access Matrix for Domain d_2

Three general observations are worth noting for an access matrix constructed for any CS system. First, subjects cannot be objects, i.e. the CORBA access control model does not have the concept of operations on principals. It only has the concept of operations on interfaces, which are objects according to the terminology of the access matrix [Lam71]. Second, since $i_k m_p \equiv i_l m_q \Leftrightarrow k \equiv l \wedge p \equiv q$ (i.e. just $p \equiv q$ is not enough for $i_k m_p \equiv i_l m_q$), as in Table 6, the semantics of operations in a general case might be different. Thus, for each subject s and object o , the content of cell $[s, o]$ is specific to the object, i.e. no operations permitted on one object could be permitted on another object because operations are semantically different for every interface unless interfaces are related via inheritance. Third, all implementations of the same

interface in a given access policy domain are represented by the same object in the access matrix; therefore, implementations of the same interface are indistinguishable from the access control point of view. This is one of the reasons policy domains are important in the CORBA access control model.

3 Support of RBAC by the CORBA Access Control Model

Among the four RBAC reference models defined by Sandhu et al [SCFY96], $RBAC_0$ is the base model. It requires only that a system has notions of users, roles, permissions and sessions. There are no constraints on the assignment of permissions to roles and users to roles. $RBAC_1$ has hierarchies of roles in addition to everything $RBAC_0$ has. $RBAC_2$ has constraints on the assignment of users to roles and permissions to roles in addition to everything $RBAC_0$ has. $RBAC_3$ combines $RBAC_1$ and $RBAC_2$. In this section, we define $RBAC_0$ and $RBAC_1$ using the language of Definition 2.1 of the CORBA protection state configuration. This will help us show the correctness of our approach to configuring a CORBA system for supporting various RBAC models.

3.1 $RBAC_0$: Base Model

For the base model $RBAC_0$, the four sets of identities are represented in CS as follows:⁹ Users in RBAC map to users in CS; Roles are represented by set A of privilege attributes of type *role*; Permissions are equivalent to the set of rights R in CS; Sessions are equivalent to principals, which are nothing but sets of security attributes, from CS AC point of view.

$RBAC_0$ definition (reprint is available in Appendix) in the language of CS is formally defined as follows:

Definition 3.1

- U, A, R, P (users, attributes of type *role*, rights, and principals, respectively)
- $PA \subseteq R \times A$, a many-to-many assignment of granted rights to security attributes of type *role* relation.
- $UA \subseteq U \times A$, a many-to-many user to security attributes of type *role* assignment relation.

⁹We do not mention CS AC domains because, as it will be shown in the example on Page 9, RBAC models can be supported in CORBA using a single domain.

- $user : P \rightarrow U$, a function mapping each principal p_i to the single user $user(p_i)$, constant for the principal lifetime, and
- $roles : P \rightarrow 2^A$, a function mapping each principal p_i to a set of privilege attributes of type role $roles(p_i) \subseteq \{ a \mid (user(p_i), a) \in A \}$ and principal p_i has the granted rights $\bigcup_{a \in roles(p_i)} \{ r \mid (r, a) \in PA \}$

It is easy to see that the definition describes a system compliant with the RBAC₀ definition provided in [SCFY96]. Given the definition, we will show how a CORBA protection system specified by a configuration language from Definition 2.1 could be used to implement a security system compliant to this definition of RBAC₀. PA relation is specified by granted rights matrix GRM . UA relation is managed by user administrators in CS that define what values of attributes of type *role* are assigned to users. However such management functionality is beyond the scope of CS specification, which means that functionality defined by UA relation is implementation-specific. An implementation of *PrincipalAuthenticator*¹⁰ initializes new principal credentials with security attributes according to UA . An example is provided in Table 1, where attributes a_1 through a_6 have the type *role*. The value of the principal's privilege attribute of the type *AccessId* is equivalent to the return value from the function $user$. An implementation of *PrincipalAuthenticator* should initialize principal credentials according to the function $roles$. Since a user in RBAC₀ can activate any subset of roles the user is assigned to, implementation of UA ensures implementation of RBAC₀. Thus, we have shown that all relations, functions and sets specified in Definition 3.1 can be directly supported by CS-compliant implementations. In order for a CS implementation to support RBAC₀ it should:

1. comply with CS standard, and
2. provide a means to administrate user-to-role assignment relation UA , and
3. provide a means for users to select through *UserSponsor* a set of roles with which they would like to activate the new principal, and

¹⁰As it was described in Section 2, a *PrincipalAuthenticator* conducts the actual authentication and creates *Credentials* object for a new principal.

4. implement *PrincipalAuthenticator* which creates principal credentials containing privilege attributes of type *role* according to relation UA , and
5. implement *PrincipalAuthenticator* which creates principal credentials containing one and only one privilege attribute of type *AccessId*.

A straightforward implementation of RBAC₀ in CS would be the one that uses privilege attributes of only type *role* for constructing granted rights tables, such as Table 3.

3.2 RBAC₁: Role Hierarchies

RBAC₁ is RBAC₀ with role hierarchies. RBAC₁ (the definition reprint is available in Appendix) in the language of CS is formally defined as follows:

Definition 3.2

- U, A, R, P, PA, UA and $user$ are unchanged from RBAC₀.
- $RH \subseteq A \times A$ is a partial order on R called the role hierarchy, written as \geq . It is the same as in [SCFY96].
- $roles : P \rightarrow 2^A$ is modified from RBAC₀ to require $roles(p_i) \subseteq \{ a \mid (\exists a' \geq a) [(users(p_i), a') \in UA] \}$ and principal p_i has the granted rights $\bigcup_{a \in roles(p_i)} \{ r \mid (\exists a'' \leq a) [(r, a'') \in PA] \}$

□

The function $roles$ is to be implemented and enforced by a *Principal Authenticator* (Figure 2 on Page 3). A user provides to a *UserSponsor* a set of roles which they want the principal to be activated with. The *PrincipalAuthenticator*, during the authentication phase with the *UserSponsor*, creates new credentials of the principal. The credentials have requested by user roles provided that they satisfy the definition of function $roles$ for RBAC₁.

A valid implementation of RBAC₁ could be one that allows a user to specify any role junior to those the user is a member of. In this case, an implementation of *PrincipalAuthenticator* activates all roles which are junior to the specified role.

In order for a CS implementation to support RBAC₁ it should:

1. implement RBAC₀, and
2. provide a means to administrate the role hierarchy relation RH , and

3. implement *PrincipalAuthenticator* which creates principal credentials containing privilege attributes of the type *role* according to relations *UA* and *RH*, as well as the function *roles*.

3.3 RBAC₂: Constraints

Constraints in RBAC are predicates that apply to *UA* and *PA* relations and the *user* and *roles* functions ([SCFY96]). Constraints on *UA* relation are to be enforced by an implementation of user administrator tools. Constraints on the functions *user* and *roles* are the responsibility of *PrincipalAuthenticator* implementation. Constraints on *PA* relation are to be enforced by an implementation of security administrator tools.

In order for a CS implementation to support RBAC₂ it should:

1. implement RBAC₀, and
2. implement support of constraints on *UA* relation user administrator tools, and
3. implement *PrincipalAuthenticator* with support of constraints on functions *user* and *roles*, and
4. enable enforcement of constraints on *PA* relation by security administration tools.

3.4 RBAC₃: RBAC₁ + RBAC₂

RBAC₃ is a combination of RBAC₁ and RBAC₂ along with possibly additional constraints on the role hierarchy. It can be implemented in CS as well. Obviously, in order for a CS implementation to support RBAC₃ it should:

1. implement RBAC₁,
2. implement RBAC₂, and
3. implement possible additional constraints on the role hierarchy.

Requirements for support of RBAC₁ and RBAC₂ by CORBA Security service implementation have been already discussed. Implementation of additional static constraints on the RBAC₁ role hierarchy is to be done by user administrator tools. For the support dynamic constraints, additional functionality in the implementation of *PrincipalAuthenticator* is required, in addition to the administrator tools.

3.5 Example

To illustrate the points made in this section, we describe a protection state of a CORBA system defined by Definition 2.1 that implements an example role hierarchy. We use an example hierarchy from [SP98] shown in Figure 3. We will show how a CORBA-based distributed system could be configured to support RBAC₁ with an example hierarchy shown on Figure 3 and to protect access to implementations of CORBA interfaces shown in Figures 4 and 5. The following access control policies describe what

Figure 4: Example CORBA Interfaces

Figure 5: Employee Interface

actions are allowed. All other actions are denied.

1. Anyone can look up an employee's name and experience.
2. Everyone in the engineering department can get a description of and report problems regarding any project.
3. Engineers, assigned to projects, can make changes and review changes related to their projects.
4. Quality engineers can inspect the quality of projects they are assigned to.

Figure 3: An Example Role Hierarchy (from [SP98])

5. Production engineers can create new releases.
6. Project leaders can close problems.
7. The director can manage employees (assign them to projects, un-assign them from projects, add new records to their experience, and fire) and close engineering projects.

We define that *effective_rights* returns a union of granted rights per attribute. We define that *combine* returns a union of rights granted in each domain.

Single Access Policy Domain Solution

In order to implement the role hierarchy in CS without using access policy domains, we introduce two new interfaces *EngineeringProject1* and *EngineeringProject2*, as shown in Figure 6. The following configuration of a system protection state could be used:

- $A = \{e, ed, e1, e2, pe1, pe2, qe1, qe2, pl1, pl2, dir\}$. All these attributes have type *role*.
- $IM = \{Employee::get_name, Employee::assign_to_project, Employee::unassign_from_project, Employee::add_experience, Employee::get_experience, Employee::fire, EngineeringProject1::inspect_quality, EngineeringProject1::make_changes, EngineeringProject1::report_problem, EngineeringProject1::review_changes, EngineeringProject1::close, EngineeringProject1::close_problem, EngineeringProject1::create_new_release, EngineeringProject1::get_description, EngineeringProject2::inspect_quality, EngineeringProject2::make_changes, EngineeringProject2::report_problem,$

Figure 6: *EngineeringProject* Interface Hierarchy

EngineeringProject2::review_changes,
 EngineeringProject2::close,
 EngineeringProject2::close_problem,
 EngineeringProject2::create_new_release,
 EngineeringProject2::get_description}.

We do not use any implementations of interface *EngineeringProject*. Only derived interfaces are used.

- $O = \{e, ed, e1, e2, pe1, pe2, qe1, qe2, pl1, pl2, dir, prj1, prj2\}$. *prj1* is an instance of *EngineeringProject1*, and *prj2* is an instance of *EngineeringProject2*. All other elements of O are instances of interface *Employee*.
- $R = \{gn, atp, ufp, ae, ge, f, mc1, rc1, iq1, rp1, cp1, cnr1, gd1, c1, mc2, rc2, iq2, rp2, cp2, cnr2, gd2, c2\}$ ¹¹
- $D = \{d1\}$
- $C = \{all\}$ – we use only one combinator.
- *RRM* is shown in Table 7. We omitted column with rights combinators because required rights for all operations have the same combinator – “all”.¹²
- $DS = \{i, d\}$
- In the *IDM*, all interface instances are in members of the only access policy domain.
- *GRM* is shown in Table 8.

Operations	Rights
Employee::get_name	gn
Employee::assign_to_project	atp
Employee::unassign_from_project	ufp
Employee::add_experience	ae
Employee::get_experience	ge
Employee::fire	f
EngineeringProject1::get_description	gd1
EngineeringProject1::inspect_quality	iq1
EngineeringProject1::make_changes	mc1
EngineeringProject1::review_changes	rc1
EngineeringProject1::report_problem	rp1
EngineeringProject1::close_problem	cp1
EngineeringProject1::create_new_release	cnr1
EngineeringProject1::close	c1
EngineeringProject2::get_description	gd2
EngineeringProject2::inspect_quality	iq2
EngineeringProject2::make_changes	mc2
EngineeringProject2::review_changes	rc2
EngineeringProject2::report_problem	rp2
EngineeringProject2::close_problem	cp2
EngineeringProject2::create_new_release	cnr2
EngineeringProject2::close	c2

Table 7: Required Rights Matrix for the Solution with Single Domain

- $effective_rights(d_j, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_l) \subseteq \bigcup_{a_i, 1 \leq i \leq l} \{r \mid r \in GRM[a_i, d_j]\}$ – union of granted rights per attribute.
- $combine(r_{1,d_1}, r_{2,d_1}, \dots, r_{1,d_p}, r_{2,d_p}, \dots, r_{m,d_p}) \subseteq \bigcup \{r \mid r \in \{r_{1,d_1} \dots r_{m,d_p}\}\}$ – union of rights granted in each domain.

The CORBA protection system configuration described above allows enforcement of the sample policies listed on Page 8. For example, a lead of project 1 with role *pl1* activated is able to invoke operations *get_name* and *get_experience* on all implementations of interface *Employee* as well as all but *close* operations on all implementations of interface *EngineeringProject1*.

¹¹We used first letters of each operation to create a corresponding right.

¹²We could have used “any” as well. When an operation’s required rights set consists of only one right, the effect of either combinator is the same.

Privilege Attribute	Rights
e	gn, ge
ed	gd1, gd2, rp1, rp2
e1	mc1, rc1
pe1	cnr1
qe1	iq1
pl1	cp1
e2	mc2, rc2
pe2	cnr1
qe2	iq1
pl2	cp1
dir	atp, ufp, ae, f, c1, c2

Table 8: Granted Rights Matrix for Single Domain Solution.

From observing the configuration of the CORBA protection system in this solution, significant administrative overhead could be noticed. The overhead is due to the gratuitous use of a separate interface (EngineeringProject(1,2)) per project. This is because we purposefully limited our solution to a single access policy domain. It could be easily shown how the unnecessary redundancy of protection system configuration data is eliminated by using access policy domains and a hierarchy of such domains. We omit the description of a solution with multiple domains due to space limitation.

4 Conclusions

In this paper, we provided a definition of protection system configuration for CORBA Security service (CS). We defined RBAC₀ and RBAC₁ models in the language of CS and described how RBAC₀-RBAC₃ could be implemented in CS. We discussed what functionality needs to be implemented, besides compliance with CS standard, in order to support RBAC models by CS. We illustrated the discussion with a single access policy domain example of CS protection system configuration, which supports a sample role-hierarchy and access policies.

Implementations compliant with the CS specification can support RBAC₀-RBAC₃. However, additional functionality non-specified by CS is required. Implementations of *PrincipalAuthenticator* interface and *User-Sponsor* need to be aware of roles and their hierarchies (RBAC₁). To support constraints (RBAC₂), a *PrincipalAuthenticator* has to enforce corresponding constraints. Tools to administer user-to-role and role-to-rights relations are also required.

The work presented in this paper sets up a framework for implementing as well as for assessing implementations of RBAC models using CS. It provides directions for CS developers to realizing RBAC in their systems. It gives criteria to users for selecting such CS implementations that support models from the RBAC₀-RBAC₃ family.

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Appendix

Definitions of RBAC models from [SCFY96]:

Definition 4.1 The $RBAC_0$ model has the following components:

- U, R, P , and S (users, roles, permissions and sessions respectively),
- $PA \subseteq P \times R$, a many-to-many permission to role assignment relation,
- $UA \subseteq U \times R$, a many-to-many user to role assignment relation,
- $user : S \rightarrow U$, a function mapping each session s_i to the single user $user(s_i)$ (constant for the session’s lifetime), and
- $roles : S \rightarrow 2^R$, a function mapping each session s_i to a set of roles $roles(s_i) \subseteq \{ r \mid (user(s_i), r) \in UA \}$ (which can change with time) and session s_i has the permissions $\bigcup_{r \in roles(s_i)} \{ p \mid (p, r) \in PA \}$

□

Definition 4.2 The $RBAC_1$ model has the following components:

- U, R, P, S, PA, UA , and $user$ are unchanged from $RBAC_0$,
- $RH \subseteq R \times R$ is a partial order on R called the role hierarchy or role dominance relation, also written as \geq , and
- $roles : S \rightarrow 2^R$ is modified from $RBAC_0$ to require $roles(s_i) \subseteq \{ r \mid (\exists r' \geq r) [(user(s_i), r') \in UA] \}$ (which can change with time) and session s_i has the permissions $\bigcup_{r \in roles(s_i)} \{ p \mid (\exists r'' \leq r) [(p, r'') \in PA] \}$

□